

Architecture Studio - III
Project Title: MOSQUE

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SEMESTER IV (FALL), 2022-23
CLASS OF 2025

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Studio Instructor: Hassan Wajid
Studio Assistant: Mahwish Khalil

PROJECT: MOSQUE
PROJECT DESIGNER: MARWA ARSHAD

Project initiative: Charcoal sketches

Brief:

- Keeping “Namaz” as the highlight of sketches, took out the essence of these emotions experienced while praying to God and drew them out into these sketches.
- Metaphorically used lights and shadows as positive and negative aspects of sentiments.
- The journey of salaah, the six steps were entitled towards these sketches as a source of purification, solitude and embracement etc.

Project Process

- **Construction of Mosque on site**
 - **Site B**
 - **About 4 Kanal of area**
- **Instructed to cover 40% built area & 60% area landscape**

Project Final

- **Plans, Sections, Elevations**
 - **Plasticine Models**
 - **Structure Models**
 - **Cardboard Models**
 - **Bubble diagrams**

Initial Sketches

Threshold

Journey Towards Purity

Threshold Towards Solitude

Sacred Space Of Spirituality

Space Of Purification

Embracing The Enlightenment

Sections-A5

Sections-A5

Case studies-1 (Modern)

Architect Name: Fluid Motion Architects, Reza Daneshmir and Catherine Spiridonoff

Building Name: Vali-e-asr Mosque

Place: Tehran, Iran

Era: It was completed in 2018

Reason for Selected Building with Reference to Miniature:

The building eschews the stereotypical typology of large domes and tall minarets in favor of a modest horizontality thereby making the mosque harmoniously co-exist with the surrounding buildings and adjacent park.

Case studies-1

Case studies-2 (old)

Architect Name: Firm Schiattarella Associati

Building Name: Al Jabri Mosque

Place: Ha'il, Saudi Arabia

Era:

Reason for Selected Building with Reference to Miniature:

This mosque provides a space where light dominates underlining its sacredness and at the same time fosters meditation and prayer fully respecting local tradition and culture.

Case studies-1

Site Plan (Scale 1/16)

Plans, Sections, Elevations (Scale 1/16)-Process Work

Plasticine Model

Structural Model

Cardboard Model

Plasticine Model

Structural Model

Cardboard Model

Experiential Drawings- Process Work

Experiential Drawings- Final

Bubble Diagram

Final Plans (Scale 1/16)

PLAN 1
ON SCALE OF 1/16"

1	MALE PRAYER HALL
2	FEMALE PRAYER HALL
3	IMAM'S RESIDENCE
4	LIBRARY
5	NIJAH'S AREA
6	MALE ABLUCTION
7	FEMALE ABLUCTION
8	COURTYARD
9	FOUNTAIN
10	RAMP
11	MUNAR
12	MINBAR

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SIR HASAN WAJIB
PROJECT: MOSQUE

Final Plans (Scale 1/16)

PLAN 2
SCALE 1/16

PLAN 3
SCALE 1/16

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SIP HASSAN
WATUB
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Sections (Scale 1/16)

Sections (Scale 1/16)

SECTION 1

SECTION 3

SECTION 2

SECTION 4

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SIR HASSAN WAJID
MAM MAHWISH KHALIL

Elevations (Scale 1/16)

EAST ELEVATION

WEST ELEVATION

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SIR HASSAN WAJI
MARWA MAHWISH

Elevations (Scale 1/16)

NORTH ELEVATION

SOUTH ELEVATION

MARWA ARSIANS 0762
(SIR HASAN WASID
MAM MAWISHI KHIL)

Model Photography

Model Photography

Model Photography

Model Photography

Conclusion

What did you learn from this project? (50 words)

Keeping “Namaz” as the highlight

This project helped me understand that the concept and idea behind the construction is important and so is the experience the space is offering. We worked with lights and shadows to define the magnitude and to create the solitude in our spaces. The emotions we feel during Namaz were broken down and incorporated in our mosque designs. The connection to Allah we feel during namaz we can also feel when we enter from the threshold of the mosque.

